

PREVENTION OF POLICE CORRUPTION

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Abstract

Police corruption is a serious security problem in the Republic of North Macedonia that needs to be addressed and investigated to find preventive policies to reduce it and increase citizens' trust in the police. Police corruption is investigated through the analysis of corruption crimes committed by police officers, but also other crimes committed by police officers through "trading with influence".

Police corruption as a serious problem is also emphasized in the reports of international institutions and bodies, where the most common factors contributing to it are indicated, such as interaction between unprofessionalism and poor organization, employment of unskilled personnel, neglect of the criteria for the selection and training of police employees. The prevention of police corruption is a challenge that needs to be investigated and, through an analysis of the situation, to work on preventive policy and contribute to improving the situation. The aim of the paper is to obtain knowledge about the state of police corruption through the application of the method of normative analysis, statistical and comparative analysis, as well as a case analysis from practice for the period 2020 - 2024.

Key words: police corruption, prevention, police officers, corruption crimes, training of police employees.

INTRODUCTION

Corruption has existed in society for a long time. Despite that fact, society has always been denying the existence of corruption and corrupt practices in general. Corruption usually emerges in connection with greed, which represents a precondition for an individual disposition to corruptive practice. Greed is not the only reason for development and survival of corruption. Corruption also develops in relation to, for instance, major social differentiation (especially in the example of poverty of civil servants), disintegration and transformation of political and economic systems, and particularly in connection with the situation in former socialist states, war and post-war periods, shift of political leaders or high state officials and similar (Dobrovsek & Mesko, 2009).

In many countries, the police force is commonly identified as one of the most corrupt governmental institutions (Transparency International, 2017b). Police-related

corruption may comprise petty corruption where, for example, the public are expected to pay bribes for alleged traffic violations; at the other end of the spectrum, corrupt police officers can conspire with criminals and organized crime gangs in the trafficking of drugs, humans and weapons (DCAF, 2012).

Police corruption is a socially harmful phenomenon of serious concern, as it constitutes criminal behaviour that occurs and persists within the ranks of authorized officials performing professional duties and police officers and employees holding official status who are expected to uphold the Constitution, laws, subordinate regulations, and established principles. Such acts involve the active non-application of legal and regulatory provisions or the passive failure to enforce laws, while simultaneously fulfilling the elements of various corruption-related criminal offences, as well as other crimes committed through the abuse of laws or “trading in influence.”

Police corruption results in public mistrust of the police, rendering it more difficult for the police to perform what should be their primary task, countering crime. It compromises the institutional integrity of a policing system and undermines its legitimacy (Hope, 2015).

Employees of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of North Macedonia (RNM) hold the status of authorized officials for performing professional works and police officers. They are obliged, in the performance of their duties and tasks, to protect and safeguard the lives and property of citizens, to respect the freedoms and rights of citizens, and to apply only those measures and means of coercion prescribed by law or other regulations. In their work, they must adhere to the principles of legality; proportionality and fairness; management regarding the effectiveness of employees; professional ethics, impartiality, and objectivity; transparency and confidentiality; accountability; prevention of conflicts of interest; and economical use of resources (Law on Internal Affairs, Official Gazette of RNM No. 60/25). All police personnel hold the status of officials as defined in the Criminal Code of RNM, Art. 122, par. 4, p. a) (Official Gazette of RM No. 37/96...248/18).

Police corruption is a phenomenon that reduces citizens' trust in the police and police actions, and it is a serious problem that needs to be continuously investigated and solutions to prevent it and raise the level of trust among citizens. Citizens have daily contact with some of the police services, and their experiences with the work, actions and decision-making of employees in the police structure, their perception, are important for the creation of preventive policies and strategies for police work.

APPEARING FORMS AND FORMS OF POLICE CORRUPTION

Corruption in the legislation of the Republic of North Macedonia is regulated in the Law on the Prevention of Corruption and Conflict of Interest (Official Gazette of the Republic of Macedonia No. 12/19), where corruption is defined as "use of functions, public authority, official duty and position for the realization of any benefit for oneself or for a friend". Defined as passive corruption - intentional action against an official who, directly or through an intermediary, solicits or receives benefits of any kind, for himself or a third party, or accepts a promise of such benefits, with the aim of acting or refraining from acting in accordance with his obligations or exercising his powers contrary to official obligations, and active corruption - intentional actions against any person who directly or through an intermediary, promises or provides benefits of any kind to an official, for him or for a third party, with the aim of acting or refraining from acting in accordance with his obligations or exercising his powers contrary to official obligations. Meanwhile, a conflict

of interest is understood as a situation in which an official has a private interest that influences or can influence the impartial exercise of his public powers or official duties.

According to the mentioned definition of corruption, both passive and active corruption are included and formed as police corruption.

Police corruption according to Ivković (Ivkovic, 2005) represents any police misconduct of performing or omitting an action performed by a police officer or an entire organizational unit with disregard for legal rules and procedures. For example: an inappropriate or illegal act committed by a police officer is one that involves taking a bribe from a driver who does not respect the laws and commits a traffic offence – running a red light (Ivkovic, 2014). Hence, police corruption is understood as deviation and inappropriate behaviour with elements of illegal actions, inappropriate practices or violation of internal rules during working hours and official duties.

The police are very susceptible to corruption from the aspect of structure or organization and from the aspect of the subculture of police officers, which manifests itself in numerous opportunities and temptations, which generates deviations within the framework of the professions (Prenzler, 2009). The police are characterized by a high degree of solidarity and identification with groups. In many respects, solidarity is good - without solidarity there can be no effective police work. But it can also contribute to police corruption. Police officers who refrain from reacting against their corrupt colleagues because of the loyalty they have towards them often fall victim to the same and have the potential to fall into the corruption scheme. "A police officer, while on duty, has the discretionary authority to decide what type of deviant behaviour he will respond to (of course, within the limits established by law). The application of this authority is the core of police work. Not every offence requires responding to the police, nor is the police always the best solution to a problem. Furthermore, the police officers usually have room to manoeuvre with their powers, such as deciding how much force should be used and whether a person should be arrested or investigated (Kua, 2019). As a result, police officers may become extremely dissatisfied and start engaging in illegal activities as a way to improve their own economic situation, or they may oppose those who ignored them and did not interfere with their progress.

Police corruption can be classified into several groups: corruption of the authorities (refers to obtaining material gain, without breaking the law); service for service (for the transfer of certain goods for the purpose of transfer to business for certain individuals or companies); opportunistic theft (theft from a person under the authority of a police officer); blackmail (accepting a bribe to earn ignoring the criminal proceedings); protection against illegal activity (police protection of persons involved in illegal activities (destruction); traces of illegal activities); direct criminal activities (a police officer commits a crime for personal gain); internal payments (trade with privileges available to police officers); setting up (the form that is most often associated with prohibited procedures with drugs, for example, setting up and replacing the index) (Králj, 2014).

Police corruption serves as a bad example for the general public. In order to encourage respect for the law, states must make an effort to guarantee that those responsible for enforcing the law set a good example. The same applies to regular police officers; The senior leaders of the police should take the reduction of corruption and inappropriate behaviour seriously but also serve as a good example (DCAF, 2012). How to suppress the corruption that exists in the authorities that should deal with the situation, instead of discovering corrupt criminal acts, police officers are corrupt. Their corruption leads to resentment among the citizens, and Academician Kambovski (Kambovski, 2005)

emphasizes in several of his works „Who does not protect from the guards". A serious problem of the so-called "internal enemy" in the police structure is that the corrupt always "talk", express "dissatisfaction", but hardly anyone reports, unless it is for the detection and clarification of an organized criminal group or a single case after a complaint from a victim.

PREVENTION OF POLICE CORRUPTION

Police structures are considered part of the state institutions that are most exposed to the risk of corruption, since police officers have police powers, and it is often assumed in the public that those powers are often manipulated for their own benefit, and even for political purposes. Reducing the risk of police corruption is an important prerequisite for the successful implementation of police reform. Progress in achieving long-term goals also depends on the introduction of instruments for the fight against corruption, which, in addition to being applied in the police, will also be applied in the overall system of state administration. For this reason, strengthening the responsibility of police officers has a crucial meaning for the purposeful fight against corruption and breaking the vicious cycle of impunity (Šumić & Laličić, 2015).

In the Republic of North Macedonia, corruption in the police is a real problem, which is pointed out by GREKO in its reports, in the Report of the Fifth Round of Evaluation in the case relating to the police, several deficiencies inherent in the sanctioning regime, which is foreseen for the violation of the rules for conflict of interest and integrity, as well as the rules against corruption, are given, for which several recommendations are given that relate to suppression of corruption in the police in the act of passing normative acts and operational procedures, of acting in the direction of building police integrity and impartiality in work. Part of the recommendations relate to employment and advancement in the police careers based on quality, expertise and education, with a reduction in the influence of politicians. (Report on the Fifth round of evaluation of GRECO No. Greco RC5(2021)2, 2021) (Strasbourg, March 22-25, 2021).

Within the framework of the Ministry of Interior Affairs, as a separate organizational unit is the Department for Internal Control, Criminal Investigations and Professional Standards whose jurisdiction is repression and prevention of police corruption. And, under the auspices of the European Union and the Council of Europe, the project "External Mechanism for the Control of the Police" was implemented, the purpose of which is to establish an external mechanism that will ensure impartiality and objectivity in dealing with cases in which there is a suspicion that criminal acts have been committed by persons with police powers and members of the prison police. The external mechanism for police control functions in practice as a supplementary mechanism to the existing mechanism for internal control in the Ministry of Interior. The external mechanism for police control will be strengthened with the formation of a special Department for investigation and prosecution of criminal offences committed by persons with police powers and members of the prison police.

The formal and institutional aspect of combating police corruption is somewhat satisfied, but the level of efficiency and effectiveness of the aforementioned services is measured by the data on reported, accused and convicted police officers for criminal offences committed within the framework of their official powers and authorities. The prevention of police corruption through the attitude of citizens is an important indicator of whether citizens recognize the forms of police corruption and who are the most corrupt in the structure of employees in the Ministry of Interior.

ANALYSIS OF RESEARCH FOR CITIZENS' ATTITUDE ON POLICE CORRUPTION

The research was conducted through an electronic questionnaire in which a total of 21 questions is systematized, of which the first 3 are dedicated to the structure of the respondents - citizens from different ethnic communities, employees in the state and private sector, pensioners and unemployed people with different levels of education. The questionnaire was completed by 83 respondents, of whom 80% are men and 20% women, 49.4% of whom are aged 36-45 years, 38.8% are aged 46-55 years, and the rest are aged 18-25, 26-35, and over 56 years. According to the level of education, 57.7% have higher education, 33% have master's degrees, 3.5% have doctorates and 5.8% have secondary education. According to the structure of the respondents, it is known that these are people who have developed their own attitudes and opinions, especially on the research problem. 18 questions were asked that relate to the subject of the research, which is the perception, attitude and opinions of citizens about police corruption.

1. Do you think that police corruption is a major problem in the Republic of North Macedonia?

Chart No. 1 shows the answers to the first question, with 81.2% giving a positive answer, only 4.7% giving a negative answer, and 14.1% not sure. This indicates the fact that citizens consider the problem of police corruption in our country to be very serious.

Chart No. 1

2. Do you know what police corruption is?

Chart No. 2

In Chart No. 2, the perception of citizens regarding their knowledge of what constitutes police corruption is evident, with a high 95.2% indicating that they know, while only 2.4% gave a negative response or were unsure. This further confirms that citizens have a high level of perception or recognition of the forms and types of police corruption.

3. How would you rate the level of seriousness of police corruption?

In Chart No. 3, it is shown that citizens assess police corruption as a serious problem at 53%, an extremely serious problem at 28.9%, a not-so-serious problem at 9.7%, not a serious problem at only 1.2%, and 7.2% have no opinion. These responses confirm the seriousness of police corruption through the perception and attitude of citizens.

Chart No. 3

4. Have you ever been in a situation where you needed to resolve an issue with a police officer, and were asked for a favour or money?

Chart No. 4

Regarding the previous questions, citizens hold a positive view on the existence of police corruption and consider it a serious problem. However, when asked whether they have personally experienced a situation of police corruption, 68.2% responded negatively, 27.1% responded positively, and 4.7% do not remember, as shown in Chart No. 4.

5. In your opinion, which police officers are in the most favourable position to engage in corruption?

In Chart No. 5, the responses to the question are shown as follows: 3.5% believe it is the police administration employees, 31.8% the border police, 1.2% the commanders, 11.8% the chiefs, 1.2% the intervention and public order police officers, 5.9% the deputy ministers, and nearly half, or 44.6%, believe that traffic police officers are in the most favourable position to engage in corruption.

Chart No. 5

6. Based on your life experience, what do you think are the reasons police officers engage in corruption?

Chart No. 6

According to the responses to the sixth question, shown in Chart No. 6, respondents expressed their views on the reasons for police corruption. A significant reason is low salaries – 57.1%, acquiring money and other benefits through one’s official position and power (“enrichment”) – 35.7%, and 3.6% each consider helping others and infiltrating criminal groups to obtain criminal proceeds as reasons. This indicates that financial motives are a significant cause of police corruption. These financial motives take two directions: supplementing the family budget due to low salaries, and, for some, acquiring “wealth”, which includes infiltrating criminal groups and enabling criminal behaviour by others at the expense of illegal actions or failure to detect crimes and offences.

7. What do you think, is police corruption the individual behaviour of a police officer, or is it part of an organized scheme within police structures?

Chart No. 7

In Chart No. 7, citizens' responses regarding their opinion on whether police corruption is an individual criminal act – 34.5% – or an organized scheme within police structures – 51.2% – are shown. The remaining 14.3% believe that both forms of police corruption are present.

8. In your opinion, where are the organized schemes for police corruption most prevalent?

Chart No. 8

In Chart No. 8, it is shown that 55.3% of respondents believe that organized schemes of police corruption occur in the border police, 38.8% in the traffic police, 3.5% in the public order police, and 2.4% in the structures of the police administration. These responses, to some extent, reflect the picture of structures with a high risk of corruption, as their official positions and authorities relate to mandatory inspections, detecting offences, and directly imposing penalties, most often through fines or confiscation of goods.

9. If you were a victim of corruption by a police officer, where would you report it?

Chart No. 9

The responses to this question, shown in Chart No. 9, indicate citizens' awareness, with 72.6% recognizing the existence of a separate organizational structure for internal control and combating police corruption – the Internal Affairs Department – and considering it the best place to report cases and how they would act if they were victims of police corruption. An interesting point is that 13.1% of citizens stated they would report or expose police corruption through the media, compared to only 1.2% who would report it to a chief or commander, indicating a lack of trust in the leadership structures.

10. Is police corruption: (soliciting a bribe, requesting a favour, or other)?

Chart No. 10

In Chart No. 10, it is shown that, according to surveyed citizens, police corruption manifests itself through soliciting a bribe – 75.3%, 10.6% consider it requesting a favour, and 14.1% believe it could be other forms.

11. In your opinion, does the police have an established system to combat corruption within its ranks – police corruption?

Chart No. 11

According to Chart No. 11, citizens are not fully convinced that a system to combat corruption within the police ranks is established, with 43.5% unsure, 21.2% responding negatively, and 35.3% responding positively. This indicates that the established system for combating police corruption is not fully functioning and is not visible to most citizens, which is a strong indicator that work is needed in this area. Visibility in addressing corruption involves the use of appropriate tools, strengthened controls over police officers in their workplaces and positions, as well as prioritizing professional development and training. Additionally, more frequent security assessments of corruption risks, planning, and implementation of measures and actions to improve the situation are essential.

12. Do you think that increased monitoring of police officers would reduce their corrupt behaviour?

Chart No. 12

The previous question reflected a lack of trust in the established system for combating police corruption. This question provides insights into citizens' opinions regarding the need for increased monitoring of police officers to help reduce corruption in their work. Chart No. 12 shows the results, with 60.7% expressing a positive view—more than half of the respondents, 11.9% responding negatively, and 27.4% expressing uncertainty regarding such controls. This indicates the need to develop policies for strengthened and regular monitoring, especially in positions with a higher risk of corrupt

actions. Therefore, continuous research should be conducted, and policy decisions should be made based on research findings to implement effective solutions.

13. Do media campaigns such as ‘Report Police Corruption’ contribute to reducing police corruption?

The purpose of this question is to gauge citizens’ opinions on external factors and influences in reducing police corruption, particularly the media, often referred to as the “fourth estate”, and their contribution to combating this problem. Respondents have a very positive view on this matter: more than half, or 54.1%, responded positively, 14.1% responded negatively, and 31.8% expressed a reserved or uncertain stance regarding these campaigns, as shown in Chart No. 13.

Chart No. 13

14. Do you think that ‘anonymous’ reports of police corruption are taken seriously and handled appropriately to detect corruption and sanction the involved police officer?

Respondents’ opinions are somewhat divided regarding “anonymous” reports of police corruption and how seriously they are taken and handled. According to Chart No. 14, 36.5% responded positively, 34.1% were uncertain, and 29.4% responded negatively. This raises a serious question regarding how anonymous reports should be received, analysed, and selected, and how decisions are made on which reports to act upon.

Chart No. 14

15. What do you think—does a detected case of police corruption and the sanctioning of police officers directly contribute to reducing police corruption?

Chart No. 15

Theory and practice emphasize that every well-detected and sanctioned case of corruption has a preventive effect. Whether citizens share this view is reflected in the responses shown in Chart No. 15. A positive response was given by 77.7% of respondents, 12.9% expressed uncertainty, and 9.4% had a negative opinion. Respondents also expressed the view that repression is the most effective form of prevention.

16. Do you think that the Ministry of Internal Affairs has a developed system to combat corruption within its ranks – police corruption?

Combating corruption within the police ranks is part of the policies that are planned and implemented. However, regarding whether the system is well-developed and delivers results, respondents show greater uncertainty: 42.4% are unsure, 23.6% responded negatively, and 34.1% responded positively. This is a strong indicator of citizens' lack of confidence in the established system for combating corruption within the police ranks or in detecting police corruption by police officers.

Chart No. 16

17. Do you think that holding seminars and providing continuous education for police officers would help reduce corruption among them?

Chart No. 17

From the perspective of the need for prevention and its strengthening to combat police corruption, a question was posed regarding the enhancement of police capacities through continuous training, education, and similar measures. The responses to this question are shown in Chart 17: 54.1% expressed a positive view, 27.1% were uncertain, and 18.9% responded negatively. This indicates that education aimed at reducing police corruption is quite important for several reasons, including understanding what constitutes corrupt acts, how to deal with pressures and corruption risks, handling the influence of previously established corrupt practices by senior colleagues, and overcoming the fear of opposing corrupt activities.

18. In your opinion, should police officers for whom evidence has been obtained proving they committed criminal acts in the course of their police duties be sanctioned by: immediate suspension from duty or filing a criminal complaint?

Chart No. 18

Respondents have a very positive view on the immediate suspension of corrupt police officers for whom evidence has been obtained, with 51.7% supporting immediate suspension, while 48.2% believe criminal complaints should also be filed. For incidents involving elements of police corruption, there should certainly be suspension, as well as the filing of criminal complaints, initiation of criminal proceedings, and appropriate sanctions.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

Based on the study conducted and the smaller-scale research on the attitude and opinion of citizens on police corruption, the following conclusions can be drawn:

- Police corruption is a serious problem in the Republic of North Macedonia, although work is underway to establish an institutional and legal framework, greater implementation and "visibility" for citizens is needed in the fight against this type of corruption.
- Police corruption is more prominent in police structures that are at a higher risk of corruption, are in positions for sanctioning (traffic offences) or cross-border control (border police), but corruption is also prevalent among police officers in the administration.
- Police officers are more susceptible to passive corruption manifested through accepting bribes without prior request or established criminal schemes that have existed for a longer period of time, and the corrupt amounts are individually low, but in total it is about acquiring high amounts of corrupt proceeds.
- Prevention of police corruption is a serious challenge that should be based on an institutional and formal framework that will be implemented through programs to suppress corruption, namely prevention through repression and prevention through education.
- Prevention by raising awareness among employees in police structures that corruption is a dangerous phenomenon, jobs are lost due to corruption, the penalties are serious, primarily prison sentences, but also work on raising awareness and conscience that we should work on detecting crime, and not on corrupt actions for not detecting crime, not sanctioning misdemeanours, and thus confirming the strong question: Who should protect us from the guards?. The guards should deal with the risks and act in accordance with the law and enable the suppression of crime and not join the ranks of criminals.

REFERENCES

- Dobovsek, B. & Mesko, G., (2009), *Prevention of corruption, Part 4, Prevention of corruption, Government of Montenegro*, The human resources management authority, Podgorica, 2009. (28 – 42)
- Ivković, Sanja Kutnjak, (2005), *Fallen Blue Knights: Controlling Police Corruption*, Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Ivković, Sanja Kutnjak, (2014), *Police Misconduct*. In *The Oxford Handbook of Police and Policing*. Edited by Michael D. Reisig and Robert J. Kane. Oxford: Oxford University Press, pp. 302–37.
- Извештај на Петтиот круг на евалуација на ГРЕКО бр. Greco RC5(2021)2, 2021)(Стразбур, 22-25 март 2021 година)
- Johnson, Cox III, 2004-2005, (2008), *Types of police corruption/misconduct OSCE*, Guidebook on Democratic Policing, Johnson, Cox III, 2004-2005, Types of police corruption/misconduct OSCE. "Guidebook on Democratic Policing." Vienna: OSCE.
- Камбовски В. , (2005), *Организиран криминал*, Скопје.
- Kappeler, V. E., Sluder, R. D., & Alpert, G. P. (1998). *Forces of deviance: Understanding the dark side of policing (2nd ed.)*. Prospect Heights, IL: Waveland Press.

- Kralj, Ž., (2014), *Korupcija u policiji*, UDK: 351.74, <https://hrcak.srce.hr/file/177888>.
- Criminal Code of RNM, *Official Gazette of RM No. 37/96...248/18*.
- Куа, Ц., (2006), *Спречување на полициската корупција во Сингапур: Улогата на регрутирањето, обуката и социјализацијата*, Списание за јавна администрација на Азија и Пацификот 28, бр. 1/06. (59-75)
- Law on Internal Affairs, *Official Gazette of RNM No. 60/25*.
- Prenzler, T., (2009), *Police Corruption: Preventing Misconducts and Maintaining Integrity*, CRC Press.
- Report on the Fifth round of evaluation of GREKO No. Greco RC5(2021)2, 2021) (Strasbourg, March 22-25, 2021)
- Прирачник за полициски интегритет, (2012), DCAF.
- Report on the Fifth evaluation round at GREKO No. Greco RC5(2021)2, 2021) (Strasbourg, March 22-25, 2021)
- Hope, K.R. (2015), *Police corruption and police reforms in developing societies*.
- Šumić, R. & Laličić, R., (2015), *Jačanje kapaciteta policije i pravosuđa u borbi protiv korupcije u Srbiji*, (PACS), Zajednički projekat Evropske Unije i Saveta Evrope, Savet Evrope, Kancelarija u Beogradu, Beograd.